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GN5-2 WP6 Incubator Project Closure Report

WFO RAG Agent and LLM Integration

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Abstract

The WFO RAG agent and LLM integration introduces a Large Language Model (LLM)-based search implementation in the Workflow Orchestrator (WFO). This incubator successfully evaluates and integrates a number of state-of-the-art technology (libraries) into the WFO, thereby creating a Retrieval Augmentation Generation (RAG) agent. This project implements an index search in a Postgres database, makes use of PydanticAI for typesafe interaction with an AI agent, leverages the AG-UI protocol to enable seamless integration into a modern typescript-based frontend web application, and implements the OpenAI API spec to enable integrations with any open source LLM capable of supporting the OpenAI API specification.

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Executive Summary

The WFO RAG agent and LLM integration incubator project run under GN5-2 [\[1\]](#) WP6 successfully developed an implementation that allows Workflow Orchestrator (WFO) software users full control of the LLM used in driving the search and agent functionality.

In doing so, the incubator has measurably increased the accuracy of search results compared to the current WFO search implementation. Furthermore, it has investigated and implemented a number of very new technologies and libraries that are available in the Generative AI ecosystem.

Key achievements of the project include:

- Scalable and successful indexing of the orchestrator database, enabling semantic, similarity and structured search.
- Exposing the new search interface to an AI agent implemented with PydanticAI [\[2\]](#) through tools.
- Implementing the Agent - User Interface (AG-UI) protocol with Copilot kit [\[3\]](#), providing a mechanism through which a UI can parse and handle the Server Side Events (SSE) that are generated by the API and the LLM.
- Dissemination of results through GitHub [\[4\]](#), NREN channels, the WFO-user group, a GEANT info-share [\[5\]](#), an extensive technical blog post [\[6\]](#) and documentation about the LLM search.

Interested NRENs are now able to instrument their orchestrator installation with an LLM (on-premises or cloud based) and reap the benefits of better search performance and extensive reporting and data analysis tools provided by the AI agent.

1 Introduction

A Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) agent is a type of AI application that combines natural language processing (NLP) and large language models (LLMs) with external knowledge retrieval mechanisms. This approach is particularly useful when interacting with complex systems such as OSS (Operations Support Systems) and BSS (Business Support Systems) platforms, as it allows the agent to provide accurate, contextualised, and up-to-date responses. The incubator project aimed to create an implementation that is integrated into the workflow orchestrator so that the user can use natural language, also known as “prompts”, to interact with the orchestration engine.

Key Components of a RAG Agent

A RAG agent is composed of:

1. **Language Model (LLM):** The core of the agent, responsible for interpreting natural language queries, generating responses, and facilitating interaction.
2. **Retrieval Mechanism:** This connects the agent to external data sources like databases, APIs, or documents. The agent retrieves relevant information to answer questions or execute tasks.
3. **Integration Layer:** Manages the communication between the language model, the retrieval system, and the external platform (in this case, OSS/BSS).

How a RAG is Developed

When creating a RAG, the developer prompts the chosen LLM with detailed instructions about what the tool supports. A RAG does not restrict the LLM choice as this is up to the user, however this project only supports the use of OpenAI API-compatible LLMs. Users can choose whether they use a self-hosted LLM or online cloud-based offerings. It is relatively easy to start small and add functionality to a RAG, as you do not need to train an AI model. At most, it may be necessary to generate the embeddings necessary for the LLM to be able to search the available data. This is a well-documented and standardised process.

The following diagram shows at a high-level the interaction that happens when a user asks a question. It is not necessary to train an AI model, the LLM is used to help extract and enhance data retrieved from a database (in this case a vector store).

Figure 1.1: Steps taken during a RAG data lookup

At step 3 in the process, RAG frameworks like Pydantic AI and/or LangChain [7] enable developers to add tools that can add extra functionality.

The next diagram shows how a RAG framework interacts with a tool to enrich the data that is retrieved from a database.

Figure 1.2: Enrichment of data by the RAG by using tools to look up extra information

Adding a tool can be any arbitrary functionality, but it can be as simple as making an API call to an external system fetching information that the LLM can use to enrich its response to the user. More complex actions can be chained together making it possible for the LLM to chain multiple tools in sequence to execute more complex tasks or queries.

Example Use Cases

Typically, where used, the WFO software is an integral part of provisioning at an NREN and manages critical functions of the network. Below are some examples of what a RAG agent could do when embedded into the WFO software and integrated in the OSS/BSS landscape. These are not deliverables of this incubator proposal but examples of tool implementations that could be created for a RAG agent:

1. Real-Time Query Resolution

Use Case: Retrieving details about subscriptions, network status, aggregation queries, closest match search.

How it works: The RAG agent processes the user's prompt, retrieves relevant information from the WFO and/or other integrated OSS/BSS systems and delivers the response. If the tooling is capable, it may also reach out to the network and query live information from the device and/or retrieve information from a historical data source.

2. Automating Workflows

Use Case: Automatic ticket creation, service activations and/or provisioning of subscriptions.

How it works: The agent interprets the prompt and uses its tooling to resolve the user's intent. If running workflows is available this is possible, but it can also use its knowledge of the WFO information and OSS/BSS information to create tickets.

3. Operational Insights and Reporting

Use Case: Generating network performance reports, the monitoring of KPIs and/or predicting service disruptions.

How it works: The RAG agent retrieves structured data from OSS/BSS, processes it, and generates user-friendly summaries or visualisations. It may also help troubleshooting when it is integrated with a logging system and/or telemetry system.

2 Project Results

The project has produced the following results:

- Code module in the orchestrator-core repository: <https://github.com/workfloworchestrator/orchestrator-core/tree/main/orchestrator/search>
- All use-cases as described in the proposal have been covered:
 - More accurate search
 - Simple RAG use case where questions like: How many subscriptions does customer X have between 2022 and 2024? How many active processes do I have? Please export this...
 - UI implementation
- UI library implementation in this repository: <https://github.com/workfloworchestrator/orchestrator-ui-library>
- Example implementation available here: <https://github.com/workfloworchestrator/example-orchestrator>
- Technical blog post by (one of) the developer(s): <https://timfrohlich.com/blog/postgresql-hybrid-search>
- GÉANT infoshare: This event showcased the output of the project. The presentation and recording are archived here: <https://events.geant.org/event/2022/>
- Benchmarking between embedding sizes and different embedding models to guarantee reliability of the results as an integration test: https://github.com/workfloworchestrator/orchestrator-core/tree/main/test/integration_tests/search
- Documentation: <https://workfloworchestrator.org/orchestrator-core>

Some example screenshots are shown below:

Figure 2.1: Screen capture of the Agent showcasing a graph of the number of subscriptions added per month as an absolute metric and cumulative metric

Figure 2.2: Screen capture of the Agent showcasing the export function

Figure 2.3: Screen capture showcasing semantic search and filtering*

*The embedding model translates the search string from English to Dutch, retrieves the relevant results and the user can filter/fine-tune by adding filter groups to the search. In this case, it is filtering on an exact match of product type L3VPN.

3 Conclusions and Future Development

This document has reported on the successful execution of the WFO RAG agent and LLM integration. During the past six months, SURF implemented and demonstrated an LLM-powered search and RAG implementation. Through integrating the output of this project, NRENs and other networking organisations can enhance their orchestrator installation with AI. The software has been architected to be LLM agnostic; this means users may use any OpenAI standard-compatible LLM on-premises or in the cloud. This work has been published online on GitHub [8] and disseminated to the wider NREN and European R&E and developers' communities via an infoshare and various posts on commonly used Slack and Discord channels.

The next steps for this work will be to:

- Increase the level of documentation by incorporating some example implementations.
- Refactor the Agent into a graph to allow more complex tool calling and usage of less complex (cheaper) LLM's.
- Implement the Agent-to-Agent interface and an MCP server in the orchestrator to enable it to exist within a constellation of AI agents.
- Refactor the UI to make the Search and Agent a first-class citizen of the orchestrator-core.

Glossary

AG-UI	Agent - User Interface
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BSS	Business Support Systems
GN5-2	GÉANT Network 5, Phase 2, a project part funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101194278 and one of the projects implementing the actions defined in the GN5-FPA
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
L3VPN	Layer 3 Virtual Private Network
LLM	Large Language Model
MCP	Model Context Protocol
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NREN	National Research and Education Network
OSS	Operations Support Systems
RAG	Retrieval-Augmented Generation
SSE	Server Side Event
UI	User Interface
WFO	Workflow Orchestrator
WP	Work Package
WP6	Work Package 6 Network Development

References

- [1] GN5-2 Project <https://geant.org/gn5-2/>
- [2] <https://ai.pydantic.dev/>
- [3] <https://www.copilotkit.ai/>
- [4] <https://github.com/workfloworchestrator/orchestrator-core>
- [5] <https://events.geant.org/event/1993/>
- [6] 'Building a Schema-Agnostic Hybrid Search System in PostgreSQL'
<https://timfrohlich.com/blog/postgresql-hybrid-search>
- [7] <https://www.langchain.com/>
- [8] <https://github.com/workfloworchestrator>